

MODERN LINGUISTICS IN TERMS OF COGNITIVE TRENDS

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Abstract.

The article discusses the notion of anthropocentric view in linguistics, formation of the anthropocentric paradigm in linguistics. Takes close look to researches done on cognitive linguistics which is considered one of the relevant fields of modern linguistics. Main trends of cognitive linguistics and their principles are discussed.

Key words: language, modern linguistics, cognitive linguistics, cognitive grammar, cognitive semantics, cognitive stylistics

The direction of text linguistics, which was formed in the second half of the XX century, poses new problems to science in the XXI century. One of such problems is the anthropocentric¹ approach to the language system. The anthropocentric paradigm is considered a major turning point in the science of linguistics and is the cause of many studies and researches.

Formation of the anthropocentric paradigm in linguistics is related to the research of the factor of the language owner - speaker. In this regard, Prof. N. Makhmudov considers that according to such an objective nature of language, in the anthropocentric paradigm, man is placed in the main place, and language is the main element that makes up the human personality.

Recognizing the superiority of the anthropocentric paradigm, scientists define the following methodological principles of modern linguistics: anthropocentrism, expansionism, and functionalism.

As mentioned above, the modern stage of the development of the science of linguistics is characterized by the emergence of various theories and directions based on interdisciplinary and anthropocentric principles. Modern linguistics consists of such interdisciplinary directions as cognitive linguistics, linguocultural studies, linguopragmatics, ethnolinguistics, neurolinguistics, and intercultural communication. In its turn, each direction has its own subject and research methods.

In modern linguistics language system and text construction was not only analyzed from a philological point of view, but the scope of this science expanded with concepts and categories related to the activities of perception, knowledge, understanding, analysis.

Cognitive linguistics, one of the relevant fields of modern linguistics, is a linguistic direction that is rapidly developing and expanding its boundaries.

¹ Anthropocentrism (derived from the Greek word "anthropos" - "man", Latin "centrum" - "center") - in this scientific direction, its main problem is man, who is the center of the universe. the anthropocentric direction examines the essence of man in close connection with language.

Cognitology (cognitive science - the science of thinking) is an interdisciplinary science that emerged at the intersection of psychology, anthropology, linguistics, sociology, computer science, neurology and philosophy. The cooperation of these fields is a phenomenon based on cognitive activity. Cognitive linguistics is also part of the sciences dealing with human cognitive activity.

According to D. U. Ashurova, M. R. Galieva, cognitive linguistics is a branch of cognitive sciences related to the study of relations between linguistic choices and mental processes, human experience and its results-knowledge. Cognitive linguistics investigates language as a cognitive mechanism for organizing, expressing, processing, storing, and transmitting layers of knowledge.²

In other words, cognitive linguistics is a separate scientific field whose object is the study of the human mind, thinking, and its mental processes and states. It is the science of cognition and knowledge, the processes of understanding the world during human activity.³

The first works that signaled the beginning of cognitive linguistics were G. Lakoff's revolutionary book "Metaphors We Live By" (1980) and "Women, Fire, and Dangerous Things" (1987). Almost simultaneously, R. Langacker published the first volume of Foundations of Cognitive Grammar (1987). Another work that left a significant mark on cognitive linguistics was the collection "Topics in Cognitive Linguistics" published in 1988.

This science has become popular among scientists in Uzbekistan. It should be noted that in foreign linguistics emphasis is placed on cognitive grammar and cognitive mechanisms of classification, while in CIS countries, including Uzbekistan, linguists pay attention to cognitive semantics. In this regard, cognitive semantics and cognitive stylistics came to the fore in Uzbekistan. (Safarov, 2006; Ashurova, 2005; 2012; 2016; Rasulova, 2005; Yusupov, 2011; Djusupov, 2011).

In Uzbekistan, many studies are devoted to the problems of cognitive linguistics, which provide a new understanding of stylistic phenomena, for example, the concept of stylistic device (Tadjibayeva, 2006; Panjiyeva, 2004; Djusupov, 2006; Galiyeva, 2010; Dusabayeva, 2009; Saliyeva, 2010, G.X.Bakiyeva).

In addition, D. U. Ashurova developed a cognitive approach to text interpretation. From this point of view, text interpretation is a purposeful cognitive activity aimed at revealing the deep conceptual content of the text. In this regard, stylistic categories such as imagery, emotiveness, implicitness, modality and intertextuality are considered as the main cognitive categories of the text, great attention is paid to the role of stylistic units in conveying conceptual information and expressing the conceptual world picture (Ashurova, 2012; 2013; 2016).

Moreover, N.M. Djusupov dealt with the most important and controversial issues of cognitive stylistics, such as "Cognitive stylistics and promotion processes in artistic text". In this study, the emergence of means of promotion based on the text of the English-language poetic and prose works of XX century British and American writers and the identification of various attractive features, cognitive processes, knowledge structures, and a set of functional signs that determine the uniqueness of their realization in the text. The cognitive-stylistic bases of the tools have been studied and analyzed.

² D.U.Ashurova, M.R.Galieva "Cognitive linguistics" 12p.

³ "Notion" and "Concept" in cognitive linguistics, methods of their analysis" Sayidrahimova N. S.

It can be mentioned that, the most complete description of the main problems of cognitive linguistics, Sh. Safarov's monograph "Cognitive Linguistics" covers the main notions and assumptions of cognitive linguistics, such as the concept and its types, conceptualization and categorization processes, frame semantics, and prototype theory.

As V. A. Maslova noted in the book "Cognitive Linguistics", the theory of linguistics should not only answer the question of what language is, but should also shed light on what a person can achieve through language. In connection with this idea, the scientist believes that cognitive linguistics has the following tasks:

- The role of language in the process of understanding and thinking about the world;
- The role of language knowledge in the process of receiving, processing and transmitting information about the world;
- Describe the processes of conceptualization and categorization of knowledge, as well as the means and methods of conceptualization and categorization of culture;
- Describing the system of universal concepts that make up the conceptosphere;

According to D.U.Ashurova cognitive Linguistics has been developing in different ways and directions, the main of which are cognitive semantics, cognitive grammar, cognitive word-formation and cognitive stylistics.

Cognitive Semantics deals with the conceptual theory of meaning which presupposes the multilevel interpretation of both linguistic and non-linguistic (encyclopedic) knowledge (Болдырев, 2004). It means that meanings correlate with certain cognitive contexts, knowledge structures, which represent these meanings and secure their understanding. In other words, meaning is a manifestation of conceptual structures, and Cognitive Semantics focuses on how language encodes and reflects conceptual structures (Evans, Green, 2006).

Meaning in its cognitive sense is characterized by a number of features: it is encyclopedic, it depends on the cognitive contexts, it is usage-based (Evans, Green, 2006). The encyclopedic nature of meaning gives access to vast resources of knowledge relating to a particular concept or conceptual domain. The notion of "concept" is the key notion of Cognitive Linguistics, as "a quantum of knowledge", a unit of the conceptual system of language.

It is acknowledged that the meaning of linguistic units depends on how language is actually used. Language use presupposes not only linguistic knowledge (paradigmatic, syntagmatic and contextual links), but also interactional and goal-directed aspects, and background knowledge.

So, Cognitive Semantics is primarily concerned with the conceptual nature of linguistic meanings, their relationships to conceptual structures, that reflect human knowledge and experience.

The theory of Frame Semantics elaborated by Ch. Fillmore (1982) presents one of the most influential theories of Cognitive Linguistics. According to Ch. Fillmore frame is a schematization of experience, a knowledge structure which relates the elements and entities associated with a particular scene from human experience. In other words, frames represent a complex knowledge structure including a group of related words and concepts. For example, THEATRE is not simply a cultural institution; it is associated with a number of concepts such as: ACTORS, SPECTATORS, PERFORMANCE, STAGE, SUCCESS, APPLAUSE, etc.

Scholars distinguish different types of frames that reflect various knowledge structures about the world:

- frame-structures for denoting notions and objects: (loan, pledge, promissory);
- frame-roles (manager, teacher, judge, client, cashier, student, engineer);
- frames-scenario (bankruptcy, imprisonment, meeting, birthday, conference);
- frame-situations (accident, wedding, shopping).

Frames represent a complex knowledge structure that allows us to understand the meaning; they provide background information against which linguistic units can be understood and used.

Cognitive Grammar is the theoretical framework which deals with grammatical categories, units, and constructions in their relationships to the processes of the world perception and cognition. It means that Cognitive Grammar places a great emphasis on the cognitive mechanisms that underlie grammar. In other words, Cognitive Grammar deals with the overall organization of grammar that focuses on meaning (Evans, Green, 2006).

So, the key assumption of Cognitive Grammar lies in the fact that grammar is viewed as a meaningful system, that grammatical units are inherently meaningful, that there are close links between grammar and lexicon, and that gives rise to the idea of a lexicon-grammar continuum. It means that grammar does not constitute an autonomous level, and that sound, meaning and grammar are inextricably linked.

The term “grammar” is used in the broad sense, where it refers to the language system as a whole, incorporating sound, meaning and morphology and syntax”.

Another fundamental principle of Cognitive Grammar is the usage-based thesis. It means that knowledge of language is first of all is how language is used. In other words, the language system is closely related to how language is actually used, and the language structure cannot be studied without taking into account the nature of language use. Language use involves interaction between speakers and listeners. It follows that interactional and goal-directed aspects of language use and context are of a central concern to Cognitive Grammar. The context of use interacts with the speaker’s intentions and plays a crucial role is how the utterance is interpreted by the listener.

Cognitive stylistics is a relatively new and rapidly developing field of language study at the interface between linguistics, literary studies and cognitive science. E. Semino defined it as the way in which linguistic analysis is systematically based on theories that relate linguistic choices to cognitive structures and processes (Semino, Culpeper, 2002). According to P. Simpson cognitive stylistics makes the main emphasis on mental representation rather than on textual representation and is aimed to shift the focus away from models of text and composition towards models that make explicit the links between the human mind and the process of reading (Simpson, 2004).

Cognitive style is the author’s individual way of conveying and presenting information, the peculiarities of its arrangement in the text/discourse related to a specific choice of cognitive operations and their preferable usage in the process of text production. Cognitive style is considered to be associated with the author’s personality, individual world picture, creative process of thinking and subjective modality.

In applying the principles and methods of cognitive linguistics to stylistics a special attention should be attached to the problem of stylistic devices. Traditionally stylistic devices have been studied from the point of view of their structural and semantic organization and stylistic functions. However, a satisfactory account of these phenomena can only be arrived at

by means of a cognitive approach. In this sense stylistic devices are regarded as means of transmitting the conceptual information of the text, representing the conceptual world picture and knowledge structures (allusion, antonomasia, symbol, cognitive metaphor, cognitive metonymy, etc).

All in all, it should be stressed that though Cognitive Linguistics is characterized by a multitude of views, problems, and approaches, it represents now one of the most expanding linguistic disciplines within a unified theoretical framework and methodology.

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